

A Rare Case of Chest Tightness Caused by Descending Aorta to Right Inferior Pulmonary Artery Fistula

Chieh-Jen Wu¹, Chun-Hung Hsueh^{1,2}, Tung-Ho Wu^{1,2}, Hsing-Lin Lin²

¹Veterans General Hospital- Kaohsiung, Taiwan

²Veterans General Hospital- Kaohsiung, Taiwan

Email: cjwu@vghks.gov.tw

Abstract:

Descending aorta to right inferior pulmonary artery fistula is a rare type of artery fistula and most frequently discovered accidentally without symptoms. Descending aorta to right inferior pulmonary artery fistula with myocardial ischemia has never been reported before. This article presents an 84-year-old male patient who suffered chest pain with diagnosis of angina pectoris and abnormal shunting from the descending aorta to the right inferior pulmonary artery. The syndrome was found after aorta computed tomography 6 years ago. Initially, the patient received a coronary stent implant. Nevertheless, the patient continues to experience chest tightness and symptoms of dyspnea with heart failure. Consequently, the growth of myocardial ischemia leads to necessary coronary bypass surgery. Before surgical bypass, endovascular embolization of the abnormal fistula by coils was carried out. All the collateral circulations were shut down and his chest pain symptoms with heart failure sign improved. Due to myocardial ischemia caused by descending aorta to right inferior pulmonary artery fistula, the physician should be aware that the descending aorta to right inferior pulmonary artery fistula could cause the symptoms that mimic angina pectoris since it has never been reported. The possibility of angina pectoris caused by descending aorta to right inferior pulmonary artery fistula should be kept in mind to avoid unnecessary coronary stent implant or surgical intervention to prevent potentially harmful inappropriate treatment.

Keywords:

Aorta, Pulmonary Artery, Fistula

Figure 2: A. White arrow indicates the anastomosis of descending aorta pulmonary artery fistula. B. The black arrow indicates the origin site of the aorta. C. Chest CT before endovascular embolization shows a lot of collateral vessels (black arrow). D. After embolization, all the collateral circulation is shut down (white arrow).

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How to become a “snuffboxer”: Data from the BAR-TAB Registry demonstrating the feasibility and safety of the distal transradial access via the anatomical snuffbox.

Karsten Schenke

Asklepios Klinik Barmbek, Department of Cardiology

Email: K.schenke@asklepios.com

Abstract:

Aims: Over the recent years transradial access has become the primary route for coronary angiography (CAG) and interventions (PCI) and has achieved class I recommendations in the ESC and AHA Guidelines. Recently a new puncture site more distally on the dorsal side of the hand in the area of the anatomical snuffbox has been developed and seen widespread use. With this registry we want to demonstrate the feasibility and safety of the distal transradial access.

Methods and results: From November 2017 until January 2019, we documented the characteristics of all patients scheduled for CAG or PCI via the right or left distal transradial access (dTRA). Patients with a palpable pulse at the distal and proximal radial artery were included. Ultrasound was not used for screening or puncture guidance. Primarily we have used dTRA only in selected cases, especially for access via the left arm since the placement of the arm for distal access is a lot more comfortable for the patient and the examiner than the standard proximal transradial access (pTRA).

In our cohort (N= 115, 87/115 = 75% male, average age: 74 years) patients with coronary artery bypass grafts (CABG) especially with usage of the left arteria mammaria interna (LIMA) represent the largest subgroup (N=40). Patients with advanced chronic kidney disease were another group of patients that we chose for dTRA since the first registries documented a significantly lower rate of chronic radial artery occlusion (RAO), thus the radial artery could be used for a later AV- shunt implantation (N = 7). Other reasons we have chosen dTRA were orthopedic reasons (N = 17), weak proximal pulse or RAO of the contralateral arm (N= 24) use of the non-dominant arm and known kinking of the ascending aorta or the truncus brachiocephalicus (N= 22). CAG or PCI was performed using the right arm in 33 cases and via the left arm in 82 cases.

Indications were acute coronary syndroms in 91 cases. Other indications including stable coronary disease, valvulopathies or reduced left ventricular function were present in 24 cases. PCI was performed in 42% of the patients (N = 48/115). A crossover to another site became necessary in 12 cases and we used the ipsi- or contralateral pTRA (N= 6) or the femoral artery (N=6).

Overall the puncture success rate was 94% (108/115) and the completion rate of the planned procedure was 91% (105/115). As expected, our data show a learning curve with a puncture success rate in the first 50% of the patients of 90% (51/57) and in the second half of the patients we achieved a nearly perfect puncture success rate of 98% (57/58).

The puncture time from holding the puncture needle until placement of the sheath was measured in 60 cases and was 64 sec. Only minor hematomas (<2cm) were encountered in two cases at the puncture site and one larger hematoma (<5cm) on the forearm that could be handled with compression. No other complications or RAO were discovered.

Conclusions: After more than a year of using the distal radial access in over 100 cases we can conclude that the method is feasible and can be apprehended after a learning curve of about 30 patients and lead to a near perfect puncture success rate. In our registry we haven't encountered any major complications, although naturally it requires trials with longer follow ups to compare the safety of the dTRA with the standard pTRA. If the first data showing a lower rate of RAO can be proven in a randomized trial the distal radial access could develop into the standard approach.

Left Ventricular End-Diastolic Strain Rate Recovered in hypothyroidism following levothyroxine replacement therapy: A strain rate imaging study

Lingyun Kong¹, Xia Gao², Xueyan Ding³, Guang Wang M.D.^{2*}, Fang Liu^{1*}

¹Beijing Tsinghua Changgung Hospital, School of Clinical Medicine, Tsinghua University, Beijing, China.

²Endocrinology Department, Beijing Chao-Yang Hospital, Capital Medical University, Beijing, China.

³Echocardiography Department, Beijing Chao-Yang Hospital, Capital Medical University, Beijing, China

Email: lingyunkong@126.com

Abstract:

Background: This study was aimed to explore the impact of overt hypothyroidism on diastolic left ventricular (LV) deformation and the effect of levothyroxine therapy using 2-dimensional speckle-tracking echocardiography (STE) strain rate (SR) imaging.

Methods: Forty-seven newly diagnosed hypothyroidic patients and 51 controls were prospectively enrolled. All participants underwent comprehensive 2-dimensional echocardiography. Besides the recently recommended parameters of LV diastolic function, strain imaging for LV systolic global longitudinal strain (GLS), and diastolic SR imaging at isovolumic relaxation period (SR_{ivr}), early (SR_e) and late (SR_a) diastole were assessed. Repeated echocardiography in hypothyroidic patients was made six months after the euthyroidic state was achieved.

Results: Hypothyroidic patients had a lower ejection fraction (EF) than the controls (68.6±5.2% vs. 71.5±4.0%, P=0.002) but all within normal range (57-80% and 64-79%, respectively). Significant difference was identified for SR_a [0.85±0.17 (/s) vs. 1.00±0.17 (/s), P=0.000] and GLS (-20.8±3.2% vs. -23.6±2.3%, P=0.000). Upon follow-up, LV SR_a [1.01±0.20 (/s), P=0.99 vs control] normalized when GLS (-21.6±3.1%, P=0.004 vs control) remained worse than the controls.

Conclusion: This study demonstrates subtle LV diastolic impairment in untreated hypothyroidic patients using SR imaging, which normalizes with short-term therapy and pre-dates GLS.

Keywords:

Left ventricular function; Diastolic dysfunction; Strain and Strain rate

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A cross sectional study of Industrial worker's Diet in relationship to Cardiovascular Health

Nasser Ahmed*, and Farry B. Jeffrey**

King's Centre for Professional Development**, Postgraduate Studies Unit, RAK, UAE

Email: Nasser.rab@gmail.com

Abstract:

Tremendously competitive and globalized business situation today demands a planned approach to direct and elevate the organization in a precise path. Human resources development is one of the main fields which require attention in successful organizations. Economy is backbone of any country and the base of economy is industry which is always depending on their workers, to get powerful economy of the country therefore it is very necessary to look for the 'Industrial workers' health

According to World Health Organization, the cardiovascular disease was the leading cause of NCD (Non-communicable diseases) deaths in 2012 and was responsible for 17.5 million deaths, or 46% of NCD caused deaths. The purpose of this study to signify a key in the development of an area of research by Identifying the importance of cardiovascular disease among industrial workers and timely measure for maintenance of their better health status. Using a cross-sectional research analysis, this study analysed the incidence of cardiovascular disease among industrial workers. Prevalence of cardiovascular disease was proven to be high. However, the awareness, treatment and the control of cardiovascular disease in this population were very low, the prevalence was higher in Indians compared to Pakistani and Bangladeshi or other nationalities, it was higher among those who were having the high cholesterol food intake and the majority was overweight or obese. It is hoped this study will inform policy makers and industrial workers (industrial or occupational workers) about management practices of good cardiovascular health. This study clearly answers the question why industrial workers are having more cardiovascular diseases than workers and further more studies are required to discuss this issue world-wide.

Cardiovascular diseases impact many people in different age groups, very often severely limiting the income and savings of impacted individuals and their families. According to World Health Organization, the cardiovascular disease was the leading cause of NCD (non-communicable diseases) deaths in 2012 and was responsible for 17.5 million deaths, or 46% of NCD deaths (WHO, 2014). Lost earnings and out of pocket health care payments weaken the socio-economic development of communities and nations, that condition blowout around the world for example, it was estimated that over the next 10 years (2006- 2015), China will lose \$558 billion in foregone national income due to the combination of heart disease, stroke, and diabetes. If current trends are allowed to continue, by 2030 an estimated 23.6 million people would die from cardiovascular disease, mainly from heart attacks and strokes (WHO, 2017). Over the last four decades, the rate of death from cardiovascular diseases (CVD) has declined in high-income countries, owing to the reduction in cardiovascular diseases (CVD) risk factors and better management. Recent studies indicate that, although the risk-factor burden is lower in low-income countries (WHO, 2014), the rates of major cardiovascular disease and death are substantially higher than high-income countries. This research had been conducted on south Asian industrial workers, so it is important to discuss about cardiovascular disease in South Asia and same time review its impact world-wide.

. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), Non-communicable diseases such as cardiovascular disease, cancer, chronic respiratory disease and diabetes cause 60% of all deaths globally, 80% of this mortality occurs in low and middle income countries (Narayan, K. M. V. & Ali, M. K., et al. 2010), Dubai's labour force depends on these low middle income countries like India, Pakistan, Bangladesh and other South Asian countries, in this populated area Cardiovascular diseases are very common due to many reasons like there is no check and balance on governmental healthcare facilities, financial issues and health education etc. Ignorance of these life threatening conditions leading them to carry this burden till they end up in hospitals. If Industrial workers would be fit physically and mentally then the result would be in the form of powerful economy and booming industrial zones. This research teaches us many facts regarding medical and social aspects of the life of Industrial workers and just little help and care can save many lives of this very important community, called Industrial workers. This study clearly answers the question why Industrial workers are having more cardiovascular diseases than other workers and further more studies are required to discuss this issue world-wide.

Keywords:

Industrial workers, cardiovascular health, Non-Communicable disease, World health organization, Blood pressure, cholesterol, diet, United Arab Emirates

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Effect and mechanism of mitochondrial ALDH2 on Notch1 signal pathway in myocardial injury in diabetic rats

Pin-Fang Kang^{1,2}, Min Tao^{1,2}, Jian-Lu Guo^{1,2}, Qin Gao^{2,3}, Bi Tang^{1,2}, Hong-Wei Ye^{2,3},
Heng Zhang^{1,2}, Hong-Ju Wang^{1,2*}.

¹The First Affiliated Hospital of Bengbu Medical College, China

²Department of Physiology, Bengbu Medical College, China

³Cardiovascular Research Center of Bengbu Medical College.

Email: 15215520622@163.com

Abstract:

Objective: To observe the effect of mitochondrial ALDH2 on Notch1 signaling pathway in diabetic myocardial injury and to explore the related molecular mechanisms.

Methods: Diabetic rats were induced by intraperitoneal injection of streptozotocin (55mg / kg) and divided into normal control group (Con), diabetic 4W group (DM 4W), diabetic 8W group (DM 8W) and diabetic 8W + ALDH2 agonist Ethanol group (DM + EtOH). One week after the model was established, rats in the DM+EtOH group were given daily drinking of 2.5% ethanol, and after 1 week, the concentration was changed to 5% ethanol for 8 weeks. The heart function of rats in each group was measured at different time points. After 8 weeks, the rats in each group were subjected to myocardial ischemia / reperfusion (I / R) model and divided into Con 8W I / R group, DM 8W I / R, DM + EtOH 8W I / R. The body weight and heart weight were measured to calculate the cardiac coefficient. The level of plasma creatine kinase (CK) and creatine kinase isozyme (CK-MB) were measured by automatic biochemical analyzer. Detection of cytochrome C (Cyt C) and TNF-a levels in rat myocardial tissue by the kit, HE staining after light microscopy myocardial tissue and cell morphology; Masson staining and PAS staining myocardial fibrosis, Western blotting was used to detect the expression of ALDH2, Notch1, jagged-1 and Hes-1 in myocardium. Immunohistochemistry was used to detect the protein of ALDH2, Notch1, Hes-1 and jagged-1 in rat myocardium. On the basis of the animal model, primary ventricular myocytes from 1 to 3 days-old SD neonatal rats were cultured and divided into normal control group (N), normal + ALDH2 agonist (N + Alda-1) (HG + Alda-1), high glucose + Alda-1 + Daidzin group (HG + Alda-1 + Daidzin), high glucose + Daidzin group with ALDH2 inhibitor (HG + Daidzin), high glucose + Alda-1 + Notch1 inhibitor DAPT (HG + Alda-1 + DAPT); Cardiomyocytes were identified by immunofluorescence; Cardiomyocyte proliferation activity was detected by CCK-8 assay; Apoptosis of cardiomyocytes was detected by flow cytometry with Annexin V-FITC / PI apoptosis detection kit Western Blotting was used to detect the expression of ALDH2, Notch1, Hes-1 and jagged-1 in each group.

Results:

1. The general situation in rats: Compared with the Con group, all groups of diabetes have different degrees of weight loss, lack of energy, increased urine output, slow activity, body hair, lack of luster and other performance, the longer the week, the more obvious performance; DM + EtOH group The above situation has been improved to varying degrees;
2. The cardiac coefficient: Compared with Con group, the body weight and heart weight of DM group and DM + EtOH group were significantly reduced ($P < 0.01$), and the DM 8W group had more weight ($P < 0.05$). The cardiac coefficient continued to increase ($P < 0.01$). Compared with DM group, the cardiac weight of DM + EtOH group decreased ($P < 0.05$) and the cardiac coefficient decreased ($P < 0.01$).
3. Ventricular hemodynamic parameters: Compared with Con group, LVIDd and LVIDs in DM 4W group and DM 8W group increased significantly ($P < 0.01$), EF% and FS% decreased significantly, and heart function decreased. In different course of diabetes, Compared with DM 4W and DM 8W groups, DM 8W group increased further ($P < 0.01$), EF% and FS% decreased further and heart function decreased further ($P < 0.01$). Compared with DM 4W and DM 8W groups, LVIDd and LVIDs ($P < 0.01$), EF% and FS% increased significantly, and heart function improved.
4. CK and CK-MB: Compared with Con group, the levels of CK and CK-MB in DM4W and DM 8W group were significantly increased ($P < 0.01$). Compared with DM 4W group, CK and CK-MB in DM group ($P < 0.01$). The levels of CK and CK-MB in DM + EtOH group were significantly lower than those in DM4W and DM 8W groups ($P < 0.01$).
5. ELISA detection of myocardial tissue CytC and TNF-a levels: Compared with Con group, the expression of CytC and TNF-a in DM 4W and DM8W groups was significantly increased ($P < 0.01$). Compared with DM4W, the level of CytC and TNF-a in DM 8W The levels of CytC and TNF-a in DM + EtOH group were significantly lower than those in DM4W and DM 8W groups ($P < 0.01$).
6. Myocardial tissue and cell morphology under light microscope in HE staining: The myocardium in Con group was clear, the arrangement of myocardial cells was regular, and the myocardial interstitial space was normal. Compared with Con group, the myocardial fibers in DM 4W group were disordered, Broadening, some mitochondrial matrix and cristae swelling; myocardial

fibrosis in DM 8W group was broken, dissolved, mitochondrial swelling degeneration, and disappearance of cristae; compared with DM 8W group, myocardial lesions in DM + EtOH group were alleviated. Compared with Con I / R group, myocardial myofibrils were dissolved and mitochondria were swollen in DM I / R group, Crest lysis and most vacuoles were formed. Compared with DM I / R group, myocardial myofibrils in DM + EtOH I / R group were arranged neatly and partially, and the mitochondrial membrane was intact and the ridge was partially blurred.

7. Masson staining and PAS staining were used to observe the myocardial fibrosis of rats in each group: Compared with Con group, collagen fiber content and PAS positive substance in DM 4W and DM 8W groups were significantly higher. With the prolongation of disease course, DM 8W group had higher collagen fiber content and PAS positive substance than DM 4W group; Compared with 4W and DM 8W groups, collagen fiber content and PAS-positive substances were significantly decreased in the DM+EtOH group. Compared with Con I/R group, collagen fiber content and PAS positive substance were significantly increased in DM I/R group; compared with DM I/R group, collagen fiber content and PAS positive substance were significantly decreased in DM+EtOH I/R group.

8. The expression of ALDH2, Notch1, Hes-1 and Jagged-1 in myocardium of rats was detected by RT-PCR, Western Blotting and immunohistochemistry: Compared with Con group, ALDH2, Notch1, , Compared with DM4W group, the expression of ALDH2, Notch1, Hes-1 and Jagged-1 in DM 8W group was further decreased compared with DM4W group. Compared with DM4W group and DM 8W group, ALDH2, Notch1, Hes -1, jagged-1 expression was significantly increased.

9. Myocardial cell viability and apoptosis rate: Compared with N group, the viability and apoptosis rate of HG group, HG + Alda-1 + Daidzin group and HG + Daidzin group were significantly increased ($p < 0.01$); The HG + Alda-1 + Daidzin group and HG + Daidzin group were significantly lower than those in HG + Alda-1 group ($P < 0.01$). Compared with HG group, the viability and apoptosis rate of HG + Alda- Cardiomyocytes activity and apoptosis rate increased ($p < 0.01$).

10. The expression of ALDH2, Notch1, Hes-1 and Jagged-1 in cardiomyocytes were detected by Western Blotting: The expression of ALDH2, Notch1, Hes-1 and jagged-1 in HG group and HG + Alda-1 + Daidzin group was lower than that in N group ($P < 0.01$). Compared with HG group, the expressions of ALDH2, Notch1, Hes-1 and jagged-1 in HG + Alda-1 group were increased The expression of ALDH2, Notch1, Hes-1, jagged-1 in -1 + Daidzin group and HG + Daidzin group was significantly decreased ($P < 0.01$)

Conclusions:

1. The enhanced expression of mitochondrial ALDH2 has a significant protective effect on diabetic cardiomyopathy. After inhibition of mitochondrial ALDH2 expression, myocardial fibrosis and apoptosis are increased, and myocardial injury is aggravated.

2. Mitochondrial ALDH2 may play a protective role in the heart by regulating Notch1 signaling pathway. Activation of ALDH2 can enhance the expression of Notch1, Hes-1, and Jagged-1. The heart rate of rats is decreased and the cardiac function is increased.

3. Activation of mitochondrial ALDH2 can protect myocardial ischemia/reperfusion injury in diabetic rats, and its mechanism may be related to activation of Notch1 signaling pathway.

4. Activation of mitochondrial ALDH2 can increase cardiomyocyte viability and improve cardiomyocyte apoptosis; after inhibiting Notch1 signaling pathway, mitochondrial ALDH2 expression is decreased, cardiomyocyte viability is decreased, and apoptosis is increased.

Keywords:

Mitochondrial ALDH2; Notch signaling; Diabetic ; mechanism research